

MAXSAR (CARTHAMNUS TINCTORIUS) - O'SIMLIGINING QO'LLANILISHI

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Annotatsiya: Maxsar (*Carthamus*) — murakkabguldoshlarga mansub bir, ikki va ko'p yillik o'tsimon o'simliklar turkumi, moyli ekin. Aksariyati O'rta dengiz atroflari, G'arbiy va O'rta Osiyoda o'sadigan 19 turi ma'lum. Dehqonchilikda *C.tinctorius* (bo'yokli M.) turi ekiladi. Vatani — Efiopiya va Afgoniston. O'rta Osiyoda qadimdan, Misr, Hindi-ston, Xitoyda miloddan avvalgi, Yevropada 18-asrdan yetishtiriladi. Yovvoyi hoddao'sishi kuzatilmagan. Hindiston, Turkiya, Eron, Xitoy, Yevropa mamlakatlari, AQSH va boshqa mamlakatlarda, shuningdek, O'rta Osiyoda faqat O'zbekistonda — Jizzax, Toshkent, Sirdaryo viloyatlarida (lalmi yerlarida) ekiladi. Bir yillik issiqsevar, qurg'oqchilikka juda chidamli ekin. Bo'yi 60— 120 sm, poyasi silliq, barglari nashtarsimon, tikanli va tikansiz. To'pguli savatcha, sariq, jigarrang. Mevasi pista, urugi oqish.

Kalit so'zlar: Hindiston, Xitoy, Jizzax, Sirdaryo, lalmikor yerlar, lansetsimon, maxsar,

Ma'lumki, O'zbekistonda maxsar ning ikki turiga mansub navlari ekib kelinmokda. Maxsar zorlarning asosiy qismida yumshoq maxsar (*Triticum aestivum*) juda oz qismida maxsar *Triticum durum*) yetishtirilmoqda. Mamlakatimizda Davlat reyestriga kiritilgan qattiq maxsar navlari asosan bahori va duvarakdir. Bu xususiyati hamda donning sifati yuqoriligini, xarid narxlari yumshoq maxsar nikidan 30-50% qimmatligini hisobga olsak ular tobora rivojlanayotgan makaron –konditer sanoati ehtiyojiga to'liq javob beradi. Maxsar doni makaron va makaron mahsulotlari tayyorlashda hamda konditer sanoatida ishlatiladigan asosiy xomashyodir. O'zbekistonda keyingi yillarda maxsar ekiladigan maydonlar bir necha baravar oshdi. Hozirda O'zbekistonning lalmikor yerlarida 15—20 ming ga maydonga ekiladi. U qurg'oqchilikka chidamli bo'lgani uchun yashil massasi oziqa uchun ham o'stiriladi. Urug'ining o'rtacha hosildorligi 10—12 s/ga, sug'oriladigan yerlarda 19—22 s/ga.

Botanik ta'rifi. Maxsar astradoshlar *Astaceae* oilasiga, *Carthamus L.* avlodiga kiradi. Uning 19 tun ma'lum, shulardan faqat bitta tur *C. tinctorius L.* madaniy. Madaniy maxsar baquwat rivojlangan, tarmoqlangan, yerga 2 m va undan ortiq chuqurlikka kirib boruvchi o'q ildiz tizimiga ega. Poyasi tik o'sadi, dag'al, oq rangda, juda ko'p shoxlaydi, bo'yi 40—90 sm. Poyasi pastdan boshlab uchigacha yoki yuqori qismidan shoxlaydi. Barglari — bandsiz, tuksiz, qalin, lansetsimon, lansensimon-oval, ellipssimon, cheti tishli yoki tekis qirrali, tikonli yoki tikonsiz. Poyasi va yon shoxlarining uchidagi barglar maydalashib, to'pgulning tashqi barg

o'ramasiga aylanadi. Mevasi — oq, tuksiz, yaltiroq, to'rt qirrali — oval, asosiga torayib boradigan pistacha. Pistachaning po'chog'i qattiq, qalqonli, qalin, pista vaznining 50—60 % ini tashkil qiladi, 1000 pistacha vazni 40—50 g.

Biologik xususiyatlari. Maxsar issiqsevar, qurg'oqchilikka chidamli, yozi quruq, qishi sovuq kontinental iqlim sharoitiga moslashgan o'simlik. U gullash va pishish fazasida issiqlikka juda talabchan bo'ladi. Maysalari 5—6 °C sovuqqa bardosh beradi. Maxsar O'zbekiston sha- roitida kuzda ekilganda maysalari yaxshi qishlab chiqadi. Kuzda ekil- gan maxsar bahorda ekilganiga nisbatan yuqori hosil beradi. Gullash davrida sernam, bulutli ob-havo kuzatilsa, gullar yomon changlanadi, pistachalar kam hosil bo'ladi, savatcha chiriy boshlaydi. Maxsar tuproqqa talabchan emas. U lalmikorlikda, sug'oriladigan mintaqadagi bo'z, o'tloq, o'tloq-bo'z tuproqlarda o'sadi. Sho'rga chidamliligi tufayli sho'r tuproqlarda ham o'sa oladi. Unumdorligi yuqori, nam bilan ta'minlangan tuproqlarda yuqori hosil beradi. Navlari. Maxsarning Milyutinskiy—114 navi O'zbekiston «G'alla» IICH birlashmasida yaratilgan. Tikonsiz, bo'yi 60—70 sm, 4—5 bi- rinchi tartib shoxlari bor. Savatchasining diametri 3,0—3,5 sm, bitta. Hozirgi vaqtda ham xalqaro bozorda qattiq maxsar ning sifatli doniga bo'lgan talab to'liq qondirilmayapti, bu esa ularning narxi oshishiga olib kelmoqda. Masalan 1 tonna sifatli maxsar doni 4 tonna makkajo'xori doniga ekvivalent hisoblanadi. O'zbekistonda esa maxsar doni noyob hisoblanib, unga bo'lgan talab qator yillardan beri qondirilmay kelmoqda. Keyingi yillarda respublikamizda maxsar yetishtirish bo'yicha sezilarli darajalarda muvaffaqiyatlarga erishildi, ammo yetishtirilgan barcha maxsar donining sifati davlat andozalariga javob beradi deb bo'lmaydi. Yaqin kelajakda Respublika axolisining yanada ko'payishi munosabati bilan uning don va un mahsulotlariga, oqsilga boy, ekologik toza turli xil qishloq xo'jalik mahsulotlariga bo'lgan extiyojini qondirish muammolarini xalq etishda sug'oriladigan maydonlar bilan bir qatorda lalmikor yerlardan ham samarali foydalanish muhim dolzarb ahamiyatga ega.

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